

THEORY OF FORMATION OF MUSICAL FEELINGS IN STUDENTS IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

Ibragimov Azamat Khakimboyevich

Teacher of Music and Culture at General Secondary School

No. 27, Khiva District, Khorezm Region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514895>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information on the importance of activities in the development of children's musical sensibilities in music lessons. There were also suggestions to increase children's musical emotionality.

Keywords: music, education system, activities, music literacy, listening to music, creativity, music performance.

Along with all other sciences, music has a special place in forming the spiritual consciousness of a mature generation. One of the most important goals of music education today is to educate theoretically and practically educated, creative and talented young people. Therefore, the skills of developing various methodological processes of improving the quality and efficiency of music education based on the requirements for the new educational content are being analyzed as a separate topic. Also, in the development and improvement of students' musical feelings in music lessons, generalization, study and analysis of information about their psychological and physiological characteristics and musical works suitable for their age are considered urgent problems.

Music has the ability to strongly influence human emotions and is an important means of introducing students to the world of sophistication and moral and ideological education. The great-grandfather of our national culture, Abu-Nasir Al-Farabi, said, "This science is useful for the health of the body," and our grandfather, Sheikh Saadi, says, "Music is a companion of the human soul." Music is a tool that develops emotional feelings that quickly affects a person.

Music education not only forms the skills of singing and listening to music, but also increases musical literacy. Also, it is of particular importance in the education of musical ability, in the development of emotions, in the development of attention and memory, in the enrichment of the world of impressions, in the formation of the scope of thinking.

Music plays an important role in the development of students' personality and human personality in general, it helps to form the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of students, to implement the education of national pride and patriotism, to develop creative skills, sophistication and artistic taste, to think serves to

expand the scope, develop musical feeling, educate independence and initiative. The subject of music lessons is related to all subjects taught in general secondary schools, including literature, visual arts, physical education, labor and other subjects. The implementation of the State Education Standard in musical education, as well as in all academic subjects, allows full use of national musical heritage. These are reflected in popular folk tunes and songs, creative activities of singers and musicians, status, shashmaqom, epics and today's modern musical activity. Such opportunities of musical art serve as a unique and unrepeatable resource for educating the new generation and for their development. From time immemorial, Uzbek music education, pedagogy, and its excellent methods have been improved on the example of the teacher-disciple tradition.

The new educational content of music education based on the state education standards, together with the musical knowledge and skills of students, promotes the development of such qualities as observation, memory strengthening, visual imagination, creativity, independence, initiative, artistic and musical taste. Therefore, the new content of musical culture education envisages raising the young generation to the level of a cultured person who can inherit our musical heritage and perceive the wealth of universal music.

The main goal is for students to learn the art of music with all its sophistication, public music activities, to perceive the artistic taste of music, sing, dance and create skills individually and in a group. Also, the main task of music education is to develop the musical talent of students, to increase their love and enthusiasm for the art of music, to create the necessary conditions for the development of the talent of students interested in the art of music, and to satisfy their artistic needs. . At the same time, in-depth study of the universal musical values of the peoples of the world ensures that the young generation can enjoy the cultural masterpieces of international prestige.

The minimum requirements for the content of the educational subject of music culture consist of a set of theoretical and practical activities, and they determine the following topics. Elementary music literacy, activities of creators of musical works, music performers, music performance, activities of singing, choir, ensemble, orchestra and symphony orchestras, musical stage works, folk and professional music, composers and composers' work, Uzbek folk instruments to know the instruments, the creative activity of famous Uzbek folk musicians and singers, musical terms and expressions, music genres, master classical music, the music of the peoples of the East and the world, their famous representatives,

status and shashmaqom, the activities of its famous performers, local Uzbek music and its famous performers, modernity in Uzbek national music and modern music, national pop music and its performers, refers to the mastery of our national music culture.¹

These topics are covered in the course of the lesson in the following educational activities through theoretical and practical exercises:

- 1. Listening to music.*
- 2. Singing as a group.*
- 3. Music literacy.*
- 4. Music creativity.*

Listening and singing music is the basis of educational content. In addition to learning them through singing and listening activities, an opportunity is created for comprehensive learning and mastering, and expression of musical descriptions through musical activities, musical activities, and creative activities. Uzbek folk music samples of musical works of Uzbek composers and composers, composers of neighboring and international nations, shashmaqom branches, samples of local music styles will be heard.

The activity of group laughter is necessary for the development of students' musical learning ability and performance skills. In the process of group singing in the class, the student tries to control his voice performance, hear and observe the performance of the teachers and accompany them together.

Uzbek folk songs, songs by Uzbek composers and composers, folklore songs related to local music styles, songs by composers of world and sister nations, folklore songs related to local music styles, examples of status expressions they sing

Music literacy is important as a theoretical unifying activity of all knowledge. Regardless of the activity (listening, performance, musical movements) from the lesson, the work on the given topic will be studied and new concepts will be formed about its features (genre, form, structure, performance). Therefore, musical literacy is not only the study of sheet music, but also a set of general knowledge and concepts that make up the general level of musical knowledge of students (performance, folk and compositional music, their differences, local styles of national music, classical music, musical notation).

Music literacy provides an understanding of musical terms, traditions, tempos, intervals, alteration signs, dynamic signs, musical expression language, simple

¹ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

musical forms and musical genres, major and minor scales. Listening to music, being able to distinguish a soloist from an accompaniment, being able to distinguish between an ensemble and an orchestra performance, being able to distinguish words and the timbre of words, developing musical taste and perception. It includes listening to samples of the works of Uzbek, sister and world composers.

Requirements for the level of preparation of high school students:

Local styles in national music practice and their connection with local dialects, other cultural and domestic traditions, knowledge of specific performance styles and musical instruments in each local style, Ferghana-Tashkent, Samarkand-Bukhara, Surkhandarya - Knowledge of Kashkadarya, Khorezm style characteristics, popular music genres (epic, big song, yallachilik, etc.), their famous performers, singers, understanding of status, shashmaqom, instruments and ways of saying. To know that ustozona music on the border of Uzbekistan has multi-disciplinary and local traditions, their similarities and compatibility, and the manifestation of local musical traditions in the field of modern music, composition and composer's creativity.

To sing two-part songs in a pure tone, to independently sing from major triad to minor triad, to perform forte and piano dynamic signs while singing, to be able to evaluate the level of performance and artistic quality of the songs performed by him and his comrades, to be able to differentiate according to local musical styles existing in the local region, to be able to distinguish bakhsh performances according to musical instruments (dombira, dutor, tambur, tor) and voice (muffled and open) styles, to be able to differentiate the performance methods of popular folk songs, professional music genres, big songs, epic songs. Distinguishing the local style variants of popular songs and chants, yor-yors, ushshoks is to distinguish the local style variants in Uzbek classical music, to understand the embodiment of local styles in Uzbek classical music, to determine the intervals given in singing vocal choir exercises, to perform dance creativity.²

All these requirements to the content of education are important in developing students' knowledge, creative abilities, and developing their musical feelings. Because all activities of music education are related to general music performance. Musical instruments performed by the student, the melody of the

² T. Kh. Ismailov; "Musical currents and the formation of Russian classical music" "Vestnik magistracy" 2021. #5 (116);

song studied during the lesson, all these develop the feelings of the students and create a process of logical thinking in them.

All types of musical activities are equally useful in developing and improving students' musical sense. The following musical activities are followed during music lessons. In a music lesson, all activities are logically interconnected on the basis of a certain topic, as a result, a logical unity of the lesson is created. Music literacy is important as a theoretical unifying activity of all activities. No matter which activity is used in the lesson, the work used in its practice is studied and new concepts are formed about its features. Therefore, musical literacy does not consist only of musical notation methods, but also consists in inculcating a general set of knowledge and concepts that make up the general part of students, the scope of musical knowledge.

It is necessary to pay special attention to the fact that in the development and improvement of students' musical feeling, the role of music perception (listening) and music literacy activities is special. These two activities lead to the implementation of all the remaining activities with an integral connection to each other. Singing activity is necessary for the development of students' music-learning ability and performance skills. In the process of group singing in the class, the student controls his voice performance, listens and observes the performances of his friends and tries to sing along with them.

After all, listening and singing educational materials constitute the educational content. Along with learning them through listening and singing activities, opportunities are created for comprehensive mastery and expression of musical descriptions through musical instruments, musical movements, and creative activities.

References:

1. Abralova M, Galiyeva D. Koshayev A. Methodical manual for teachers. Tashkent, G'. Publishing house named after Ghulam - printing creative house., 2008;
2. Avliyokulov N. Kh. Modern teaching technologies. Tashkent, 2001;
3. T. Kh. Ismailov; "Musical currents and the formation of Russian classical music" "Vestnik magistracy" 2021. #5 (116);
4. Begmatov S., D. Karimova 6th grade. "Music" textbooks T., 2008
5. Hasanov A. "Music and education", Tashkent, "Teacher", 1993;
6. Karimova D. "Basics of musical pedagogical skills" T., TDPU., 2008
7. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.

